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Direct Infusion Workflow

Overall study design

Title of the study				Platelet lipidomics indicates enhanced thrombocyte activation in APS in vivo (FIA-QQQ)			
Document creation date		07/30/2024		Corresponding Email		gerhard.liebisch@ukr.de	
Principal investigator		Gerhard Liebisch		Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?		Targeted	
Institution		Institute of Clinical Chemistry and Laboratory Medicine, University Hospital Regensburg		Clinical		Yes	

Lipid extraction

Extraction method				2-phase system				Were internal standards added prior extraction?				Yes			
pH adjustment		None		Special conditions		-									
2-phase system		Bligh&Dyer		Derivatization		-									

Analytical platform

Ionization additives	Ammonium acetate	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	0.8
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	Low resolution
MS type	QQQ	Resolution at MS2	Unit
MS vendor	Waters	Recording mode of raw data at MS2	Profile mode
Direct type	FIA	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No
MS Level	MS2		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Solvent blank, Internal standard blank	Type of QC sample	Sample pool

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	Yes	Precision	Yes
Lipid recovery	Yes	Accuracy	Yes
Dynamic quantification range	No	Guidelines followed	None
Limit of quantitation (LOQ)/Limit of detection (LOD)	Yes		

Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Available on request	Raw data upload	Available on request
Are metadata available?	Available on request	Additional comments	-

Sample Descriptions

Platelets, activated platelets and lipid release / Human / Cells

Storage and collection conditions	Available	Storage time (month)	18
Provided preanalytical information	Time to freeze (min), Storage time (month), Freeze-thaw cycles	Freeze-thaw cycles	1
Temperature handling original sample	Room temperature	Additives	None
Instant sample preparation	No	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Time to freeze (min)	180	Additional preservation methods	No
Snap freezing in liquid N2	No	Biobank samples	No
Storage temperature	-80 °C		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Which assumptions were presumed?	Presence of acyl-bond for all species
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction
Fragment name			
-HG(PE,141)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

1) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PE 14:0/14:0, PE 20:0/20:0 (di-phytanoyl)	-HG(PE,141)	all PE species	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	PE 20:0/20:0 was preferred for quantification, the second standard was used for sample internal QC-check.
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

2) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE	Which assumptions were presumed?	Presence of acyl-bond for all species
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction
Fragment name			
-HG(PE,141)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

2) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
LPE 13:0, LPE 18:1[D7]	-HG(PE,141)	all LPE species	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	LPE 18:1[D7] was preferred for quantification, the second standard was used for sample internal QC-check.
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

3) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC	Which assumptions were presumed?	Presence of acyl-bond for all species
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor) ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction
Fragment name			
HG(PC,184)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

3) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
LPC 13:0, LPC 19:0, HG(PC,184)		all LPC species	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	LPC 13:0 was preferred for quantification, the second standard was used for sample internal QC-check.
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

4) PS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PS	Which assumptions were presumed?	Presence of acyl-bond for all species
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction
Fragment name			
-HG(PS,185)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

4) PS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PS 15:0/18:1[D7], PS 20:0/20:0 (di-phytanoyl)	-HG(PS,185)	all PS species	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	PS 15:0/18:1[D7] was preferred for quantification, the second standard was used for sample internal QC-check.
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

5) PI[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PI	Which assumptions were presumed?	Presence of acyl-bond for all species
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction
Fragment name			
-HG(PI,277)			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

5) PI[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s)	MS2	Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
PI 15:0/18:1[D7]	-HG(PI,277)	all PI species	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	-
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

6) Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Cer	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragments for identification	Fragment name	Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction
	LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2)		
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	Both [M+H] ⁺ and [M+H-H2O] ⁺ were acquired.

6) Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
Cer 18:1;O2/14:0, Cer 18:1;O2[D7]/17:0	LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2), LCB 18:1;O2[D7](-H3O2)	all Cer species	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	Cer 18:1;O2[D7]/17:0 was preferred for quantification, the second standard was used for sample internal QC-check. Sum of [M+H] ⁺ and [M+H-H2O] ⁺ was used for quantification.
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

7) HexCer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	HexCer	Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap, In-source fragmentation
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction
Fragment name	LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2)		
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	Both [M+H] ⁺ and [M+H-H2O] ⁺ were acquired.

7) HexCer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2	Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2		Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass	
GlcCer 18:1;O2/17:0, GlcCer 18:1;O2[D5]/18:0	LCB 18:1;O2(-H3O2), LCB 18:1;O2[D5](-H3O2)	all HexCer species	
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount	Batch correction	No
Response correction	No	Further quantification remarks	GlcCer 18:1;O2[D5]/18:0 was preferred for quantification, the second standard was used for sample internal QC-check. Sum of [M+H] ⁺ and [M+H-H2O] ⁺ was used for quantification.
Type I isotope correction	Yes		

8) PE P[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE P	Which assumptions were presumed?	Presence of acyl-bond for all species
MS Level for identification	MS2	Check on:	Isomeric overlap, Isobaric overlap
Identification level	Species level	Limit of detection	Signal threshold
Polarity mode	Positive	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Lipid Identification Software	Homemade
Fragments for identification		Data manipulation	Smoothing, Centroiding, Background subtraction
Fragment name			
Plasmalogen specific fragment			
Isotope correction at MS2	Type 2	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	Yes
MS2 verified by standard	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Background check at MS2	Yes	Further identification remarks	-
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	Yes		

8) PE P[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative		Yes	Limit of quantification	Signal threshold
MS Level for quantification	MS2		Normalization to reference	Yes
Internal lipid standard(s) MS2			Lipid Quantification Software	Homemade
Internal standard	Fragment(s)	Endogenous subclass		
PE 14:0/14:0, PE 20:0/20:0 (di-phytanoyl)	Plasmalogen specificall fragment	PE P species		
Type of quantification	Internal standard amount		Batch correction	No
Response correction	No		Further quantification remarks	PE 20:0/20:0 (di-phytanoyl) was preferred for quantification, the second standard was used for sample internal QC-check.
Type I isotope correction	Yes			